

Ex situ fungal conservation: the role of culture collections

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Abstract. Fungi merit protection no less than other living organisms. This is best effected using when *ex situ* conservation complements *in situ* conservation. *Ex situ* conservation means preservation and maintenance of fungal genetic resources in pure culture. Culture collections (“genetic resource collections” and “biological resource centres”) play a key role in successful storage of fungal strains. Special organizations direct global co-ordination of culture collection activities in conservation, research, and sustainable use of genetic resources. In Russia the largest culture collection preserving fungi (and various groups of micro-organisms) is the All-Russian Culture Collection (VKM), with over 5000 fungal strains. *Ex situ* conservation of macromycete diversity is carried out by the Komarov Botanical Institute *Basidiomycetes* Culture Collection (LE–BIN), a specialized collection maintaining taxonomic diversity of macromycetes with an emphasis on rare, endangered and ectomycorrhizal species, medicinal fungi, and strains useful for biotechnology. Currently that collection maintains over 1600 strains of about 600 species from 184 genera, 51 families, and 8 orders of macromycetes. The LE–BIN culture collection has been developed for *ex situ* conservation of as many macromycete species as possible.

Key words: conservation *ex situ*, culture collections, fungi, macromycetes diversity

Introduction

“The kingdom of fungi, during its long evolution, has contributed to the formation of essential components of ecosystems, resulting in a valuable resource for human health and nutrition, for the environmental equilibrium of planet earth and the socio-economic development of rural communities.” This is a paragraph from the *Declaration of Córdoba* – the communiqué resulting from the *First World Conference on the Conservation and Sustainable Use of Wild Fungi* (Córdoba, Spain, 2007), where for the first time global principles for fungal conservation were formulated (www.cybertruffle.org.uk/whitbymycosynod/decofcor.pdf). It encapsulates the reasons why, over the past few years, fungi playing a significant role in the daily life of human beings have started to become part of the conservation programme. Fungi are used in industry, agriculture, medicine, food, textiles, bioremediation, natural cycling, and in many other ways. Fungal biotechnology has become an integral part of our life. Conservation of fungi is important, and international and

national mycological organizations are finally starting to take the issue on board: the *European Council for the Conservation of Fungi* [ECCF], is typical, having been established with the aim of making fungal protection in European countries a continuing process, not just a series of short-term projects.

While the importance of fungal conservation is unquestionable, it is not easy to protect organisms which are often invisible to the unaided eye. The real total number of fungal species is still only very approximately estimated, and a full inventory of fungal diversity is ideally the first step in any fungal conservation initiative. Over the past decades, various mycologists have attempted to calculate the true extent of fungal species diversity. The current number of described fungal species globally is between 80000 and 97000 from which over 20000 species are macrofungi. But the number of species which actually exist is likely to be much higher, and has been estimated by different authors as 700000–1500000, including 53000–140000 species of macrofungi (Hawksworth 1991, 2001; Kirk *et al.* 2001, 2008; Mueller *et al.* 2007; Schmit & Mueller 2007).

In situ and ex situ fungal conservation compared

There are two approaches to fungal conservation: *in situ* (on-site) and *ex situ* (off-site). *In situ* protection is the more immediately evident, seeking to conserve fungi in their natural habitat together with their associated plants. This generally means protecting natural habitats themselves, so that fungal populations are maintained in their natural ecotopes. Unfortunately estimates suggest that about half of the world's plant species may qualify as threatened under IUCN criteria. Fungi obligately associated with those particular plants are therefore also equally or even more endangered. Given current estimates of fungal species numbers, on average, for every lost flowering plant, approximately 6 obligately associated species of fungi are also lost (Hawksworth 2001, 2004). Human impacts on the environment create so many threats to biodiversity, including habitat loss, conversion of forests to farmlands, pollution, and many others having the greatest effect on numbers of species, that sometimes there is no other way to protect endangered species than to use *ex situ* conservation.

Conservation *ex situ* achieves protection by maintaining the fungal gene pool in culture collections. *Ex situ* conservation removes a living sample of the species from its natural ecological context and preserves it in pure culture. It is usually a supplement to *in-situ* conservation and can also be a last resort, but it cannot recreate the habitat as a whole: the entire genetic variation of a species, its symbiotic counterparts, or those elements which, over time, might help a species adapt to its changing surroundings. However, when extinction of a species in nature is imminent, *ex-situ* conservation may become the only option to preserve it. Other benefits of *ex situ* conservation lie in using and multiplying the genetic resources of fungi for scientific and practical purposes, for fundamental mycological research, biotechnology, medicine and other uses.

The role of Fungal Culture Collections

Fungal Culture Collections (CCs) play a key role in successful preservation and maintenance of fungal genetic resources. The main functions of culture collections are *ex situ* conservation of fungi, research and development of the biological resources, and provision of high quality biological material for research and industry. They serve as repositories for patent deposit strains and strains cited in scientific papers that can be used for confirmation of results and for further study. Demands on CCs change as technologies evolve and new uses of organisms are discovered. In recent years many organizations have renamed their CCs as "Genetic Resource Collections" (GRCs) and "Biological Resource Centres" (BRCs). As defined by the Organisation of Economic and Development BRC Initiative, their objective is to operate according to international quality criteria, enhance the value and application of strains and provide vital information about maintained resources (Smith 2003). The *World Federation for Culture Collections* (WFCC) and the *European Culture Collection Organisation* (ECCO) are the main co-ordinators of work on fungal conservation *ex situ*. They bring together collections and users, co-ordinate activities, and exchange information and technologies.

Fungi can only be isolated into culture manually from fruit-body tissue, spores or mycelium in or on a substratum. The aim of preservation is to maintain purity, viability and genomic integrity, avoid selection of variants, and lessen the prospects of strain deterioration. Selection of preservation method depends on the organism in question and available time, facilities and resources. The main methods for fungal preservation are shown in Table 1. Basic methods for preservation of *Basidiomycetes* are sub-culturing, storage in water and oil. These are simple and economical but the resulting storage time is not long. Although cases are known where strains have survived transfer intervals much larger than noted in the table, they usually require frequent sub-culturing which carries a contamination risk, and

Table 1. Methods for fungi preservation (Smith & Ryan 2004)

Method	Suitable for:	What is preserved?	Storage time
Basic methods			
Repeated sub-culture	Most culturable fungi	Inocula of spores or mycellium	From 2wks to 1 year
Water	Most fungi	Agar plugs	Up to 2 years
Oil	Most fungi	Slope culture	1-2 years depending on species
Silica gel	Sporulating fungi	Spores	Up to 25 years
Soil	Some sporulating fungi	Spores	Up to 10 years
Modern methods			
Lyophilization (freeze drying)	Sporulating fungi	Inocula of spores or mycellium in ampoules	Up to 50 years
Cryopreservation (mecanical deep-freeze)	Most fungi	Inocula of spores or mycellium in cryovials	Up to 40 years
Cryopreservation (liquid nitrogen)	Most fungi	Inocula of spores or mycellium in cryovials	Potentially indefinitely

Fig. 1. Number of CCs registered with the WFCC. **Fig. 2.** Number of strains preserved in the CCs (WFCC data). **Fig. 3.** Number of strains preserved in large CCs (Ryan & Smith 2004) (ATCC – American Type Culture Collection, BCCM – Belgium Co-ordinated Collection, IMI – CABI Bioscience, CCFC – Canadian Collection of Fungal Cultures, CBS – Centraalbureau voor Schimmelcultures, IFO – Institute of Fermentation Osaka, FGSC – Fungal Genetic Stock Centre, IBT – IBT Culture Collection of Fungi, MAFF – MAFF Genebank, NRRL – USDA ARS Culture Collection **Fig. 4.** Mycological Building in the Komarov Botanical Institute, St. Petersburg, Russia. **Fig. 5.** Macromycetes culturing in the LE-BIN

may result in strain drift and culture deterioration. More recent and useful methods are freeze drying and cryopreservation, which provide long-term security and reduced deterioration of strains. But these are much more complex, expensive and require special techniques, making them applicable usually only in large CCs, GRCs, and BRCs. Most fungi survive the cryopreservation process; the preserved cultures are extremely stable and storage duration time is potentially unlimited (Ryan & Smith 2004; Smith & Ryan 2004).

At the time of writing (February 2010), 571 CCs in 68 countries are registered in the *World Database Centre for Micro-organisms* (WDCM). Numbers of CCs registered in the WDCM for each continent are shown in Fig. 1, and the number of cultures preserved in these collections in Fig. 2. In total, these CCs preserve 1536237 strains of which 490238 are fungi, comprising 25186 species or sub-species (<http://wdcm.nig.ac.jp/statistics.html>). Fungal names used for strains preserved in CCs do, however, need critical revision

Fig. 6. Field works (Caucasus, Guzeripl, 2003). Identification (A) and culturing (B) of macromycetes. **Fig. 7.** Number of macromycetes cultures obtained for *ex situ* conservation in the LE–BIN in 2005–2009. **Fig. 8.** Mycological expedition 2009 at the Teberda Nature Reserve

to eliminate synonyms and duplications. The proportion of preserved strains to accepted species names has been estimated as approximately 22:1 (Hawksworth 1991, 2004). Applying this ratio to current holdings, probably around 22300 fungal species currently receive some sort of *ex situ* conservation. The number of *Basidiomycetes* listed by the WFCC has been estimated as over 3600 species (Belova *et al.* 2005).

The largest world public service collections, holding over 10000 fungal cultures, include the USDA ARS Culture Collection (NRRL) and the American Type Culture Collection (ATCC), both based in the USA, and the Centraalbureau voor Schimmelcultures (CBS) in the Netherlands (Fig. 3). The CBS is a particularly good example of an advanced culture collection. It plays a leading role both in terms of number of preserved strains and in species representation. As one of the oldest collections of living fungi in the world, it has enormous utility and prospects; it has become a leader in fungal systematics and mycological expertise (Crous *et al.* 2004; Samson *et al.* 2004).

Information about strains of many of the fungi in these larger collections is available via on-line catalogues provided directly by the individual collections or via databases such as WDCM. These big culture collections are supported by expert taxonomists and other specialized technical staff, allowing the collections to operate to high standards, ensuring that

their holdings are correctly characterized and authenticated. Unfortunately, even in large collections, a balanced coverage of all fungal groups is seldom possible. Of species which are in these collections, most are represented by very few isolates worldwide, a level which does not reflect the full genome variability (Ryan & Smith 2004).

In practice, not all fungal species can be cultured and preserved *ex situ*. Given the figures of about 90000 species of fungi described worldwide and around 22300 species preserved in CCs, it means that collectively only about 25% of known fungal diversity benefits from *ex situ* conservation, while some 75% are dependent entirely on *in situ* conservation. It is a primary imperative, therefore, that world CCs should culture as many different fungi as possible, developing methods to conserve so-called “unculturable” species. It is just as important to preserve *ex situ* strains representing nomenclatural types as to deposit voucher dried preserved material for taxonomical revision and verification of the strain.

Two important Culture Collections in Russia

In Russia the biggest CC maintaining fungal cultures is the All-Russian Collection of Micro-organisms (VKM). The current holding is over 5000 fungal strains of 1500 species

Fig. 9. *Xerula radicata*: A – in nature, B – fruiting in culture (*X. radicata* 1885). **Fig.10.** Macromycetes strains in the LE-BIN. **Fig. 11.** Fruiting in culture: A – *Flammulina velutipes* 1483, B – *Lampteromyces japonicus* 0491, C – *Agrocybe aegerita* 0552

belonging to 500 genera. *VKM Catalogue* is available on the Collection website (www.vkm.ru). On the VKM website, a database *Fungal Diversity in Culture collections* (FungalDC) has also been made available, which contains over 24500 fungal species from culture collections around the world, nearly 19000 names of fungal species/variants from *GenBank* (www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/taxonomy) and 16843 genera from the *Dictionary of the Fungi* (Kirk *et al.* 2008). Most names have links to the data bases *Mycobank* (www.mycobank.org) and *IndexFungorum* (www.indexfungorum.org). When changes occur in its data sources, the database is updated.

An example of a more specialized research institute CC is the Komarov Botanical Institute *Basidiomycetes* Culture Collection (LE–BIN) in St Petersburg, Russia (Figs 4–5). It was established in the late 1950s for study of biologically active compounds and enzymes in basidiomycetes. In the late 1990s, a new project based on the idea of macromycete conservation *ex situ* started in the Collection. The Collection's development plan was altered to include conservation *ex situ* of taxonomical and ecological diversity of basidiomycetes in Russia with emphases on preserving rare and endangered species, maintaining ectomycorrhizal fungi, and culturing species strains useful for biotechnology and medicine. The objective was to preserve *ex situ* and study in culture as many different macromycete species as possible, following the 3-step culturing process: collection and identification, isolation and verification, cultivation and investigation.

Most of the Collection strains are original isolates from field works in various regions of Russia (European areas, the Caucasus, Urals, Siberia, and Far East) mainly in protected zones, i.e. nature reserves and national parks (Fig. 6), but there are many strains from territories of the former USSR and other countries. Species and strain diversity involved in conservation *ex situ* is gradually increasing in the LE–BIN Collection (Fig. 7). During field seasons of the last 5 years (2005–2009) over 600 isolates from about 300 macromycete species were cultured. Collecting was carried out in the following regions of Russia: 2005 (Kamchatka oblast, Bystrinsky Nature Park; Primorskyi krai, Kedrovaya Pad Nature Reserve); 2006 (Rostov oblast; Krasnodarskyi krai, Sochinsky National Park and Kavkazsky Nature Reserve); 2007 (Bryansk, Leningrad and Pskov oblasts); 2008 (Altai and the Altai Republic; Moscow oblast); 2009 (Caucasus Mountains, Teberda Nature Reserve (Fig. 8); Pskov oblast; Perm oblast, Urals). Original specimens were identified by taxonomist specialists in various groups of macromycetes. Voucher specimens for maintaining cultures were preserved in the Mycological Dried Reference Collection of the Komarov Botanical Institute (LE).

Cultures maintained in the Collection are mainly of saprotrophic mushrooms including xylophages, litter decomposers, soil saprotrophs, and fungi growing in nature on various other substrata such as buried wood, cones, humus, grass, conifer needles, coal, and mosses. There are also cultures of several ectomycorrhizal fungi (e.g. species of *Amanita*, *Boletus*, and *Suillus*). In the collection, strains are maintained as sub-cultures in tubes on beer-ale (4° Balling) agar (2%)

slants at 4–6°C, and in screw-cap vials under distilled water at room temperature.

LE–BIN is now the largest living collection of basidiomycetes in Russia, preserving approximately 10% of the natural diversity of these fungi in Russia – over 1600 strains of about 600 species from 184 genera, 51 families, and 8 orders of agaricoid, aphylophoroid, and gasteroid fungi ordered according to the system set out in the 9th edition of Ainsworth and Bisby's *Dictionary of the Fungi* (Kirk *et al.* 2001). Names of LE–BIN cultures are regularly updated following modern nomenclature primarily as set out in *Index Fungorum* (www.indexfungorum.org). Primary research out with cultures from LE–BIN includes verification of cultures by a cumulative approach (using cultural, biochemical, and molecular methods); morphological, physiological and biochemical study of various macromycete taxa; fruiting of macromycetes in culture; screening for enzymes and biological active compounds (Figs 9–11). The latest edition of the *Collection Catalogue* was published in 2007 (Psurtseva *et al.* 2007).

Conclusions

Fungi provide a fascinating and almost endless source of biological diversity which, if used sustainably, can be a rich source of benefit for humans. Fungal diversity needs to be studied, and fungi need to be preserved because it is becoming evident that large numbers of species may be threatened. Culture collections play an important role in fungal conservation, and best results can be achieved using a combined approach involving *in situ* conservation, preserving fungi and their natural habitats, and *ex situ*, preserving fungal gene pools in culture collections. Briefly, it can be formulated as conservation *in situ* + conservation *ex situ* = fungal diversity for human welfare. Only in this way we can protect and use known fungal diversity, and discover and describe fungi which still unknown.

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